

HELMINTH OF PARASITES TO A PERSON NEGATIVE EFFECT AND OF INFECTION PREVENTION GET.

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Abstract: Worms it is a parasite worms considered animals, plants and basically to people parasitism by doing lives and develops and increases. Ours in our country More than 60 worms type have. To statistics according to, land of the planet out of every 3 people one worms-parasites by affected.

Key words: depend, discharge, surroundings, helminths, physically, tissues, discomfort, cleaning, Nails.

Estimate in the world life during any times worm didn't happen person no, har one person never otherwise 1 time get sick. Modern medicine information that's it shows that many diseases worms existence with depend. For example, memory decrease, navel around pain, vision of sharpness decline, own from equals physically and mentally from development behind stay, sleep teeth creaking and from his mouth saliva discharge, anal hole at night surroundings itching because of in children discomfort

HOW ARE WORMS TRANSMITTED?

- ~ Soil and water through;
- ~ Contact : animals with when playing
- ~ Alimentary: good not cooked meat, fish or sausage products;
- ~ Insects sting through;

DETERMINE THE PRESENCE OF WORM IN CHILDREN

In humans worm presence sure or hidden will be

Clearly to the signs without reason weight loss, skin of color paleness, chronic exhaustion, anal hole around evening itching

Hidden in case while before known didn't happen internal a member diseases the climax to get reason will be

SYMPTOMS OF WORM

In the body helminths existence signs differently to be it is possible while which parasite type the body into entered depend

Worm parasites of the donor body where in the field activity looking two to the category divided

➤ **Gastrointestinal** _ _ of the system different in divisions living worms _ Intestine 100 ha of parasites near type and of the intestine each one part for There are dozens of species. Thin in the intestine ascarides, antilosts, wide straps and another their" relatives". lives _Thin intestine small strap oysters and others to live with the place will be." Medical in literature one person different different parasite types with one of time in itself damaged cases are also described done

➤ **Tissues** — worms in organs, tissues and even in the blood located _ Modern medicine paragonimosis (lungs), cysticercosis (brain), echinococcosis (liver) and filariasis (

lymphatic veins) with successful struggling is coming Some of worms larvae blood system through organism across moving, har how to the member random merger can If eggs a lot if, the whole organism damage can.

Helminthosis to the signs the following includes:

- himself feel bad;
- chronic exhaustion;
- spiritual depression;
- have an appetite decline or increase;
- heart nausea sometimes vomiting;
- navel around sharp pains;
- sleep during teeth creaking;
- fast weight loss _
- defecation violation (int hardening and disorder)
- parasites and their parts or eggs garbage with comes out;
- around the anus evening itching;
- insomnia.

A WELL-KNOWN INSPECTION METHOD WHEN CHECKING WORM:

Har one the situation separately treatment for of course diagnostic inspection what we spent to the goal is compatible with:

- ~ general blood analysis;
- ~ general garbage analysis;
- ~anal hole around the skin scratch check _

TREATMENT

Antihelminthic preparations toxic , poisonous to the feature have that it was because of , to the child harm delivered don't leave in order to caution measures to see need_ Doctor to gelment against drug drugs recommendation when doing it when , how much amount and how in case to drink need about sure information take _ And that's it strictly action to do necessary. Most the main one is arbitrariness with to treatment do n't try Medicine drugs only doctor instruction according to apply a must

In children helminthosis prevention

Disease from treatment according to his prevention get important is considered Helminths with not to be harmed conditions very easy and effective , only to them compliance if done that it was They are the following:

From eating 2 times before hands soap with Hot in the water wash

Nails always take walk

Young children their clothes replace stand up

Children his room always cleaning up stand up

Young with a child in houses home animals do not save;

1 time a year to gelments against family treated stand up

Take a walk during children his hands into their mouths that they don't put considerate to be.

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